

MULTI-SCALE DEVELOPMENT OF CFRP PRESSURE VESSELS FOR LIQUID HYDROGEN APPLICATION

ICCM23, BELFAST

Marina Wolff¹, Birte Höck¹, Markus Quadt²

¹ MT Aerospace AG, Franz-Josef-Strauß-Straße 5, 86153 Augsburg, Germany, marina.wolff@mt-aerospace.de, www.mt-aerospace.de

² ArianeGroup GmbH, Airbus-Allee 1, 28361 Bremen, Germany, markus.quadt@ariane.group

- ▶ **OH B SE** one of the largest European space companies
 - Revenue 1 BN€
 - ~ 3000 employees
- ▶ **MT Aerospace AG** is the launcher division of OH B
 - Established in 1969
 - ~ 500 employees
 - Revenue 122 M€ (2021)

Space

- ▶ Launcher
- ▶ Spacecraft
- ▶ Satellite Components
- ▶ Structures & Tanks
- ▶ Development & Manufacturing

Aeronautics & Defence

- ▶ Water Tanks & Structures
- ▶ Development & Manufacturing

Infrastructure & Ground Services

- ▶ Ground Infrastructure
- ▶ Launch Site Operations

MT AEROSPACE – WHAT WE DO

Matured over decades to a Tier 1 Aerospace Supplier

LARGE MACHINING

ADVANCED FORMING

WELDING (FSW / EB / TTG)

ASSEMBLY

ADDITIVE MANUFACTURING

AUTOMATED FIBER PLACEMENT

WINDING

SANDWICH
LIGHT-RTM

HYBRID

OUT OF AUTOCLAVE

ADVANCED NDI

TESTING

SYSTEM ENGINEERING

ANALYSIS & SIMULATION
DESIGN

ICARUS - FUTURE COMPOSITE UPPER STAGE FOR ARIANE 6

▶ Upper Stage Evolutions

- Ariane 6 upper stage ULPM (**Upper Liquid Propulsion Module**) is currently mainly composed of aluminium primary structures
- Only exceptions are the **Upper Part (UP)** and the **Interface Structure (IFS)** between ULPM and main stage (LLPM), which are made out of carbon fibre composite material
- The upper stage dry mass is one important parameter for the payload performance
- To reduce the upper stage dry mass a step wise approach is used:
 - Increment #1: a mass reduction of 250 kg
 - Increment #2: a mass reduction of 550 kg
 - ICARUS: full composite upper stage with a mass reduction of 1500 kg

PROJECT PHOEBUS

- Prototype of a **Highly OptimizEd Black Upper Stage**
- ESA Future **Launchers Preparatory Programme (FLPP)**
- Demonstration of mechanical, thermal, functional and economic superiority of a CFRP (**C**arbon **F**iber **R**einforced **P**lastic) upper stage on a scaled ground test demonstrator (d ≈ 3.5m)
- Phase C: performed under prime contract ArianeGroup Bremen and MT Aerospace as design definition authority for bare tanks and structures
- Work share (mechanics aspects: MT Aerospace – functional and thermal aspects: ArianeGroup):
 - Main components of the demonstrator like both bare tanks and the inter-tank structure are manufactured at MT Aerospace in Augsburg
 - ArianeGroup manufactures the Fluidic Integrated Thrust frame (FLINT) below the LOx tank
 - Integration and assembly is performed at the A6 ULPM Final Assembly Line (FAL) at ArianeGroup in Bremen
 - Functional testing under the lead of ArianeGroup at the DLR facilities in Lampoldshausen

© ArianeGroup
PHOEBUS demonstrator - CAD view

PHOEBUS UPPER STAGE DEMONSTRATOR

- ▶ Main objectives are
 - To mature technology, manufacturing and industrial readiness level (TRL, MRL and IRL) to 6
 - To reduce the stage mass at a considerable scale
 - To demonstrate the expected mechanical and functional characteristics and the operability of a CFRP cryogenic upper stage
 - To project the real field data from the demonstrator on a future upper stage serial production
 - ▶ After a technology screening the most challenging topics identified are
 - LH2 leak tightness
 - LOx compatibility
 - CFRP manhole flange/cover connection
 - Core suspension: CFRP suitable design feature for bifurcation area between tank dome, tank cylinder and skirt
 - Evacuated core insulation: outer sandwich cylinder of the LH2 tank is evacuated, eliminating the need for an additional external thermal insulation
 - LOx Tank Attachment Structure (LTAS)
- **Based on this screening, technology topics (TTs) and technology control vehicles (TCVs \triangleq scaled bread boards) are defined and tested**

© ArianeGroup
PHOEBUS demonstrator

Reference A6
Upper Stage

Comparison of payload and cost performance to Ariane 6 upper stage for tanks and intertank structures

Target Application

Target Application configuration trade off depending on configuration and loading

Demonstrator Cryogenic Ground
Stage Test

Verification of mechanical, thermal, functional and economic performance up to TRL 6

Technology maturation and risk reduction on
TCVs and TTs

Aim: Reduction of technological risks before implementing technologies into the demonstrator

- ▶ New technologies are investigated in detail in Technology Topics (TTs) (TRL 3)
- ▶ Technology Control Vehicles (TCVs \triangleq subscale breadboards) are developed, manufactured and tested (TRL 4)

TARGET APPLICATION TRADE OFF SELECTED REFERENCE CONFIGURATION

*Chosen target application
configuration for PHOEBUS*

LOX Tank Suspension-Configuration

- LH2 tank $\varnothing \approx 5.4$ m
- LOX tank $\varnothing \approx 3.6$ m
- LOX tank suspension via X-bracket LTAS

Reference from ESA-FLPP MUSE
upper stage system trade-off
(ArianeGroup)

Most balanced between mass, cost,
industrial performance and
technological risk.

- ▶ Major functional challenges of a CFRP upper stage tanks (liner-free Type V)
 - LH2 leak-tightness
 - LOx compatibility

- ▶ LH2 leak-tightness requirement given by ArianeGroup
 - Requirements given for different temperatures, pressures and durations for domes and cylindrical regions

- ▶ Objective: off-the-shelf CFRP material

- ▶ Step-by-step development and verification approach

LH2 LEAK-TIGHTNESS AND LOX COMPATIBILITY DEVELOPMENT AND VERIFICATION APPROACH

PHOEBUS ground demonstrator – 2025:

- Verification of key technologies at near full scale level
- Tested under representative loading – cryogenic test (1g environment)
- Verification of mechanical, thermal, functional and economical performance

$\varnothing \approx 3.5$ m

Ground Demonstrator with LH2 and LOX (led by ArianeGroup)

TCV – End 2023

- Tested under representative loading
- Prove of LH2 leak-tightness / LOX compatibility
 - Mechanical justification
 - Verification of manufacturing quality
 - Improve of numerical methods

$\varnothing \approx 2$ m

Sub-scale Breadboard (TCV) with LH2 and LOX

Understanding of leak-tightness under multiaxial loading

Test Elements at RT and 77K

Characterization of used materials

- Degradation due to temperature
- Understanding of Diffusion (w/o loading)

Coupon Samples at RT and 77K

- ▶ Permeation at RT on flat samples with He (without loading)
 - Depending on CFRP material leakage occurs short term ($< 1\text{h}$) or long term ($> 24\text{h}$)

➔ Leak-tightness requirement must be a function of time

- ▶ Permeation at 77K on flat samples with He (without loading)

- Leakage is not an issue long-term ➔ He molecules have lower kinematic energy at cryogenic temperatures

➔ Leak-tightness requirement must be a function of temperature

- Acceptance requirement: at RT, but only during acceptance test (minutes \triangleq short term)
- Operations requirement: at cryogenic temperatures, but for hours (\triangleq long term)

- ▶ Unidirectional tensile tests at RT and 77K to understand mechanical degradation (ULL = Unidirectional load leak test)

- Depending on CFRP material matrix performance decreases drastically
- Materials with highly toughened matrix systems show very promising results

➔ Leak-tightness requirement must be a function of loading

Permeation of CFRP materials at RT

ULL test set-up

- ▶ Multidirectional strain state with respect to leakage at RT and cryogenic
 - Depending on the position in the tank different strain states are present (e. g. dome vs cylinder)
 - To cover these strain states bulge and MLL (multidirectional load leak) tests were investigated
 - ➔ Both tests have limitations in test conduction and evaluation
 - ➔ Replaced with bottle tests (multiaxial loading)

- ▶ LOx compatibility tests
 - ➔ A holistic LOX compatibility logic with respect to critical energy was agreed between MT Aerospace and Ariane Group Bremen
 - ➔ Pressure surge test showed that all materials are GOX compatible

LH2 LEAK-TIGHTNESS AND LOX COMPATIBILITY TEST RESULTS: TEST ELEMENTS

- ▶ Multidirectional tensile tests at RT and 77K of flat samples verified that materials with highly toughened matrix systems are promising candidates
- ▶ 80-litre pressurized bottles designed and manufactured by MT Aerospace
 - Under the applied thermo-mechanical loading a similar stress-strain state is present in the bottle laminate as for the target application
 - Test sequence:
 1. Initial leak test at RT for low, artificial delta pressure (\triangleq requirement for metallic tanks)
 2. He leakage at representative pressure and ≈ 120 K
 3. H₂ leakage at representative pressure and 20K
 4. Recheck of global leak tightness with 1) and 2)
 5. LO_x compatibility campaign at representative pressure and 90K including impact event
 6. Recheck of global leak tightness with 1) and 2)
 7. Cryogenic temperature cycling at 77K and representative pressure
 8. Recheck of global leak tightness with 1) and 2)

LH₂ bottle test @ DLR Trauen

LO_x bottle test @ Rheinmetall

► One material was successful in LH2 and LOX test campaign

- Both requirements of LH2 leak tightness and LOx compatibility were fulfilled
- Local and global leak rate do not change between the initial leak tightness check and the re-checks after LH2 and LOx test campaigns
- After additional six cryogenic cycles the global leak rate exceeded the requirement because the material degraded locally at several positions
- Local measurement shows still leak rates below the requirement
- Based on these results and micrographs a material law was defined to predict leak tightness for future applications

► Core Suspension

- Connection of the pressure vessel with the unpressurised outer sandwich cylinder
- Combines two functions in one element:
 - Structural connection: it decouples the different strains from tank and skirt, but is capable to transmit inertia loads between tank and the outer sandwich tube
 - Thermal insulation: the sandwich design contributes to the thermal insulation of the tank

TT: Core suspension samples

► Evacuated Sandwich of outer tube

- Combines two functions in one element:
 - Transfer of the general loads
 - Thermal insulation of the LH2 tank
- The “functional integration” is a significant contributor to reduce the structural mass and the propellant boil-off of the composite upper stage

TT: Evacuated sandwich

- ▶ LH2-TCV1 and LOx-TCV6 are structural tanks with $d \approx 1.9$ m and $l \approx 2.0$ m (LH2-TCV1 incl. ELS) and $l \approx 1.5$ m (LOx-TCV6)
 - Main focus of the TCVs is the LH2 leak tightness and LOx compatibility of the pressure vessel
 - Secondary objectives
 - Verification of core suspension (Y-joint) performance between vessel and tube
 - Verification of insulation performance of outer tube evacuated sandwich
 - Following test campaigns are defined for the TCVs:
 1. RT tests with He up to artificial delta pressure:
To demonstrate the leak tightness at RT
 2. LN2 tests (acceptance test):
To measure strains and deformations under cryogenic temperature and internal pressure and ensure structural safety for LH2/LOx tests (acceptance test)
 3. LH2/LOx tests:
To simulate fill, pressurization and drain cycles. Measurement of mechanical strains, deformations, temperature fields and leakage under cryogenic conditions and inner pressure
 4. LN2 tests with external mechanical loads:
To evaluate the structural response of the core suspension and outer sandwich tube under cryogenic temperatures, inner pressure and flux load

LH2-TCV1 (left), LOx-TCV6 (right)

LH2 AND LOX STRUCTURAL TANKS

LH2-TCV1 AND LOX-TCV6

- ▶ Both TCVs are designed and manufactured at MT Aerospace in Augsburg
 - Strength and LH2 leak tightness justification
 - Based on a nonlinear analysis using ABAQUS
 - To implement non-symmetrical effects a 360° global model is used combined with detailed models
 - Digital process simulation was part of the design loop
 - Digital interfaces between manufacturing and CAD/FE software guarantee that the design definition is always ensured
- LOx-TCV6 is manufactured → test in autumn 2023
- The pressure vessel of LH2-TCV1 is already manufactured → currently manufacturing of outer tube

*FE-model of
LOx-TCV6*

*Manufacturing
(top) and Test
Rigs (bottom) of
Tank-TCVs:
LH2-TCV1 (left),
LOx-TCV6 (right)*

- ▶ Manhole flanges (MHF) and covers are part of the pressure vessel
 - High wall thicknesses necessary due to interfaces
 - ➔ high impact on pressure vessel mass
 - ➔ aim in PHOEBUS to not only have CFRP tank shells, but also CFRP manhole flanges and covers
 - Bolted connected must be reusable to have access into the tanks at every phase of the stage assembly
 - Upper and lower cover do not look similar due to different interfaces
 - Integral manhole flange chosen (no separate flange): tank shell is locally thickened at the pole region, where the bolted connection and sealing will be present

Manhole flange and cover

MBB of lower cover

CFRP MANHOLE FLANGE AND COVER

TCV20: CFRP MANHOLE FLANGE AND COVER

- ▶ TCV20 is a half CFRP tank including tank shell, manhole flange and cover ($d \approx 2.5$ m, $l \approx 0.3$ m)
 - The diameter of the flange and cover is the same as for the target application
 - LH2 leak tightness checked with helium at 77 K in combination with inner pressure
 - Different leak paths possible, e.g. main sealing or through the wall thickness of the parts
 - TCV20 is designed and manufactured at MT Aerospace in Augsburg
 - Complex lay-up strategy close to the pole: a transition zone of polar placed plies coming from the tank shell and Cartesian placed plies is necessary
 - ➔ Create degree of exchange between strength/LH2 leak tightness justification and process simulation necessary
 - TCV20 test in December 2023

TCV20: CFRP manhole flange and cover

*MBB of TCV20
left: lower cover,
right: tank shell
with integral
manhole flange*

PHOEBUS PROJECT

CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

MT AEROSPACE

An OHB Company

- ▶ The requirements for the TCVs and the PHOEBUS demonstrator H/W were derived from the system requirements of the target application ICARUS by ArianeGroup in Bremen
- ▶ TCVs are currently manufactured according to the design and justification by MT Aerospace
 - ➔ TRL level will be 5 after successfully testing of the TCVs in 2023
- ▶ The manufacturing of the PHOEBUS demonstrator H/W will start in autumn 2023
- ▶ The functional testing is scheduled for 2025 using the DLR facilities in Lampoldshausen
 - ➔ A successful functional test would demonstrate a TRL close to 6
- ▶ A final design loop for the target application is planned to implement the technical expertise into the target application design definition

PHOEBUS demonstrator - CAD view

© ArianeGroup

© ArianeGroup

A6 with CFRP Upper Stage ICARUS

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

- ▶ MT Aerospace and ArianeGroup would like to thank our customers. The development of a ground demonstrator for maturing technologies, which are key for a future Ariane 6 CFRP upper stage, is only possible thanks to the German funding of the DLR Agency via ESA's Future Launchers Preparatory Programme (FLPP).
- ▶ Furthermore, we thank all our partners, especially Rheinmetall Waffe Munition as well as the DLR institutes in Bremen, Trauen, and Lampoldshausen for the good collaboration.

GERMANY

MT Aerospace AG

Franz-Josef-Strauß-Straße 5
86153 Augsburg
Germany
+49 (0)821 505-01

FRENCH GUIANA

MT Aerospace Guyane S.A.S.

Résidence Mme Paille
25-27, rue Branly
97319 Kourou
Cedex/France
+594 (0)594 3275 90
